

Determinants of Cervical Cancer Screening Uptake Among Women of Reproductive Age in Akwa Ibom Northwest Senatorial District, Nigeria

Ntong, Margaret Aloysius¹; Usen, Ofonime Emmanuel² & Agba, Amira Sampson³

^{1,2&3}Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education
Faculty of Education, University of Uyo, Uyo

ntongmargaret3@gmail.com¹, usenofonime95@gmail.com²,
agbaamira8@gmail.com³
08163302948¹, 08032706130², 07064394628³

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Abstract

Cervical cancer remains a significant public health challenge, particularly in low- and middle-income countries like Nigeria. Despite advancements in preventive healthcare and the availability of effective screening methods, the uptake among women of reproductive age remains critically low. This study investigated the determinants of cervical cancer screening uptake among women aged 15–49 in the Akwa Ibom Northwest Senatorial District. A descriptive cross-sectional survey design was employed, using a stratified random sampling technique to select participants from both urban and rural areas. The study specifically examined how knowledge, educational qualification, income, and religion influence cervical cancer screening practices. Data were collected through structured questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive statistics, chi-square tests for associations, and multiple regression analysis to determine predictive relationships. Results showed significant disparities in screening knowledge and behavior between urban and rural women, with educational attainment and income positively associated with screening uptake. Religious beliefs also significantly influenced women's willingness to participate in screening programs. Based on these findings, the study recommends targeted health education campaigns, economic support strategies, and culturally

sensitive community engagement (particularly involving religious and traditional leaders) to improve cervical cancer screening rates and reduce mortality among women in the region.

Keywords: Cervical cancer, screening uptake, reproductive health, education, income, religion, Nigeria, Akwa Ibom

1.1 Introduction

Cervical cancer is one of the most preventable yet persistently deadly forms of cancer affecting women, particularly those in their reproductive years. Globally, it ranks as the fourth most common cancer among women, with an estimated 604,127 new cases and 341,831 deaths recorded in 2020 alone (WHO, 2020). Despite being largely preventable through early detection and treatment of precancerous lesions, cervical cancer continues to claim thousands of lives each year, especially in low- and middle-income countries, where access to screening and treatment services is limited. Sub-Saharan Africa bears a disproportionate burden, with some of the highest incidence and mortality rates worldwide.

In Nigeria, cervical cancer is the second most prevalent cancer among women and has overtaken other major health concerns such as HIV/AIDS in some regions. Each year, approximately 10,000 Nigerian women develop cervical cancer, and around 8,000 die from the disease (Uchendu, 2020). This high mortality rate is largely attributable to late detection, driven by low screening uptake. While effective screening methods, such as the Pap smear test, Visual Inspection with Acetic Acid (VIA), and Human Papillomavirus (HPV) testing, are available, their utilization remains alarmingly low across the country.

The World Health Organization (2021) has emphasized the role of early detection and regular screening in drastically reducing both the incidence and mortality of cervical cancer. However, screening uptake in Nigeria is hindered by a complex interplay of personal, socio-economic, cultural, and religious factors. These include limited awareness of cervical cancer and its screening methods, low income, limited access to healthcare facilities, negative religious perceptions, and poor education levels among women, especially those living in rural areas.

Akwa Ibom State, located in the South-South region of Nigeria, is not exempt from this national trend. Within the Akwa Ibom Northwest Senatorial District, the situation reflects a broader national concern: despite efforts by governmental and non-governmental organizations to promote awareness and provide services, the rate of cervical cancer screening remains insufficient. This is particularly troubling given the

reported prevalence of cervical cancer in the region, affecting women at their most productive and economically active ages.

Understanding the underlying factors that influence women's participation in cervical cancer screening is therefore essential for effective intervention. Studies have shown that a woman's level of knowledge about cervical cancer, her educational background, income level, and religious beliefs significantly affect her likelihood of undergoing screening. For instance, women with higher education levels are more likely to understand the importance of screening and access healthcare services. Similarly, low-income women often face financial and logistical barriers, while certain religious doctrines may discourage medical intervention, including preventive health services.

This study is designed to assess the influence of these personal determinants, specifically knowledge, education, income, and religion, on the practice of cervical cancer screening among women of reproductive age in Akwa Ibom Northwest Senatorial District. By identifying the specific barriers and enablers within this demographic, the research aims to inform context-sensitive strategies that can improve screening uptake and ultimately reduce cervical cancer-related morbidity and mortality in the region.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Cervical cancer remains one of the leading causes of cancer-related deaths among women in Nigeria, despite being largely preventable and treatable when detected early. In recent years, the burden of this disease has increased, particularly among women of reproductive age who are economically and socially vital to their families and communities. The World Health Organization (2020) reports that Nigeria records over 10,000 new cases annually, with approximately 8,000 deaths—figures that reflect late-stage diagnosis and poor screening practices.

Although early screening has been proven effective in reducing cervical cancer incidence and mortality, its uptake remains dismally low in many parts of the country, including the Akwa Ibom Northwest Senatorial District. A multitude of factors may explain this persistent gap in preventive health behavior, including insufficient knowledge about cervical cancer and the importance of screening, particularly among rural women. Moreover, educational attainment has been shown to significantly affect health literacy and decision-making, yet the influence of educational qualification on screening behavior in this region remains underexplored.

Also, socio-economic constraints such as low-income limit women's ability to access health services, while religious beliefs and practices may further inhibit the willingness to engage in cervical cancer screening. Some religious communities discourage medical

interventions or promote fatalistic views that deter women from seeking preventive care. The compounded effect of these personal and socio-cultural factors contributes to the ongoing underutilization of screening services and subsequent late-stage detection.

Given the high prevalence of cervical cancer in Nigeria and the preventable nature of the disease through timely screening, it is imperative to investigate these influencing factors comprehensively. Understanding the specific barriers within the Akwa Ibom Northwest Senatorial District will provide critical insights into why many women of reproductive age are not participating in screening programs, thereby informing more effective, targeted interventions.

1.3 Significance of the Study

This study holds significant value for multiple stakeholders concerned with women's health, cancer prevention, and public health planning in Nigeria. Firstly, for women of reproductive age in Akwa Ibom Northwest Senatorial District, the study highlights critical knowledge gaps and barriers that hinder cervical cancer screening, potentially empowering them to make informed health choices. Increased awareness and understanding may lead to improved screening behavior and earlier detection of cervical abnormalities.

For health educators and community health workers, the findings will provide evidence-based direction for developing tailored health promotion strategies. By identifying the specific knowledge deficits and socio-cultural inhibitors, they can design more effective awareness campaigns and community-based interventions that resonate with both urban and rural women.

Policy makers and government health authorities stand to benefit from the study's insights into how educational qualification, income levels, and religious beliefs influence screening practices. These findings can guide the formulation of policies that address inequalities in health education, improve access to affordable screening services, and integrate culturally sensitive health education into reproductive health programs.

Religious and community leaders may also find the study useful, as it reveals the role of religious beliefs in shaping health behavior. Engaging these leaders in advocacy can help dispel myths and promote positive health practices within communities.

Finally, for researchers and scholars, the study adds to the growing body of literature on cervical cancer screening uptake in low-resource settings, offering a regional perspective that may support comparative studies and broader public health strategies. And ultimately, the significance of this research lies in its potential to contribute to the reduction of cervical cancer incidence and mortality through informed policy, targeted education, and culturally relevant interventions.

1.4 Objectives of the Study

- i. To assess the knowledge of cervical cancer screening among urban and rural women of reproductive age.
- ii. To examine the influence of educational qualification on the practice of cervical cancer screening.
- iii. To determine the influence of income and religion on the practice of cervical cancer screening.

1.5 Research Questions

- i. What differences exist in the knowledge of cervical cancer screening between urban and rural women of reproductive age?
- ii. How does educational qualification influence the practice of cervical cancer screening?
- iii. What are the effects of income and religion on the practice of cervical cancer screening among women of reproductive age?

1.6 Research Hypotheses

- i. There is no significant influence of location on the knowledge of cervical cancer screening.
- ii. There is no significant influence of educational qualification on the practice of cervical cancer screening.
- iii. There is no significant influence of income and religion on the practice of cervical cancer screening.

2.1 Literature Review

2.1.1 Knowledge of Cervical Cancer Screening

Cervical cancer screening is a critical public health intervention aimed at detecting pre-cancerous changes in the cervix before they develop into full-blown cancer. Despite the availability of effective screening methods such as Pap smear, Visual Inspection with Acetic Acid (VIA), and HPV testing, the uptake remains low, especially in developing countries. According to the World Health Organization (2021), lack of awareness and insufficient knowledge about cervical cancer are major contributing factors to the low screening rate in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Several studies corroborate this assertion. For instance, Akokuwebe et al. (2021) found that only 33% of female students in South Africa had heard of cervical cancer screening, and even fewer understood its preventive potential. Similarly, Tsegaye et al. (2022) in Ethiopia reported that more than half of their respondents lacked knowledge of cervical cancer symptoms, risk factors, and preventive measures. In Nigeria, Olubodun et al. (2022) revealed that 81.7% of women diagnosed with high-grade cervical lesions had

no prior knowledge of cervical cancer. This lack of knowledge prevents timely screening, leading to diagnoses at advanced stages of the disease.

Moreover, knowledge of where to access screening services also plays a critical role. WHO (2022) emphasized that awareness alone is not sufficient; knowledge must be coupled with accessibility to services. In Akwa Ibom, such knowledge gaps are compounded by limited outreach and education programs, especially in rural communities. Hence, knowledge remains a foundational determinant of screening behavior.

2.1.2 Educational Qualification and Screening Practice

Education has consistently been identified as a social determinant of health and a key factor in the uptake of preventive health services. Educated women are more likely to possess health literacy, comprehend medical information, and take proactive health decisions. Ginsburg et al. (2020) posit that formal education acts as a “social vaccine” against disease, particularly in resource-constrained settings.

A study by Iliyasu et al. (2020) in Northern Nigeria found that women with tertiary education were significantly more likely to have heard of cervical cancer and be willing to undergo HPV vaccination. Similarly, Hailu (2021) discovered a strong association between higher levels of education and better knowledge, attitude, and practice of cervical cancer screening among health science students in Ethiopia.

In contrast, Mafiana et al. (2022) observed that in some Nigerian communities, even educated women had poor screening practices, suggesting that education alone may not be sufficient without supporting awareness campaigns and accessible screening services. Nevertheless, the consensus remains that education enhances critical thinking and decision-making, thereby improving health-seeking behavior.

2.1.3 Influence of Income on Screening Practice

Income level directly affects access to healthcare, including cervical cancer screening. Low-income women often prioritize immediate survival needs over preventive healthcare, resulting in lower screening rates. Cho et al. (2022) documented that poverty is strongly associated with lower life expectancy and higher mortality, particularly in cancer-related illnesses.

Sharma et al. (2021) found that low-income women were twice as likely to forgo cervical cancer screening compared to those in higher income brackets. Similarly, a study in Botswana by Rendle et al. (2022) highlighted that screening adherence would increase from 54% to 74% if cost barriers were removed. These findings emphasize the financial burden associated with screening services, including transportation, consultation, and laboratory fees, which collectively deter women from participating.

In Nigeria, where a large proportion of the population lives below the poverty line, many women lack the financial capacity to access even the most basic preventive services. Addressing income-based disparities is thus essential to improve screening coverage.

2.1.4 Influence of Religion on Screening Practice

Religious beliefs and teachings significantly influence health behaviors, including attitudes toward medical interventions such as cervical cancer screening. In some communities, faith-based ideologies discourage reliance on medical treatment, viewing illness as a test of faith or divine punishment. Jackson et al. (2020) noted that in certain Christian denominations, medical screening is perceived as a lack of faith, leading adherents to rely solely on prayer.

Studies conducted in Sub-Saharan Africa have shown that religious barriers contribute to low screening uptake. Mengesha et al. (2020) reported that women who believed cancer was a punishment from God were significantly less likely to participate in screening programs. In a Congolese study, those who viewed divine intervention as the only viable solution to illness rarely engaged with health services.

However, not all religious influences are negative. Some religious communities promote health-seeking behaviors and encourage women to utilize available health services. The key lies in engaging religious leaders as advocates for preventive healthcare. In the context of Akwa Ibom, where religious adherence is strong, understanding these dynamics is crucial for designing culturally sensitive health interventions.

2.1.5 Synthesis and Research Gap

While the literature clearly identifies knowledge, education, income, and religion as major determinants of cervical cancer screening, few studies have examined these variables in an integrated manner within a localized context like Akwa Ibom Northwest Senatorial District. Existing national and regional studies often generalize findings without accounting for the unique socio-cultural and economic landscape of specific areas.

This study seeks to bridge this gap by investigating how these factors collectively influence screening practices among women of reproductive age in the study area. By doing so, it aims to generate evidence-based recommendations tailored to the local context.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on three key behavioral health theories that provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing women's participation in

cervical cancer screening: the Health Belief Model (HBM), the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), and the Locus of Control Theory. These theories offer insights into how personal beliefs, intentions, and perceived control over health outcomes shape decision-making regarding preventive health behaviors such as cervical cancer screening.

2.2.1 Health Belief Model (HBM)

Developed in the 1950s by Rosenstock, Hochbaum, Kegeles, and Leventhal, the Health Belief Model (HBM) is a widely used psychological framework for understanding health-related behaviors. The model posits that individuals are more likely to engage in a health behavior such as cancer screening, if they perceive themselves to be susceptible to a disease, believe the disease has serious consequences, believe that a course of action (e.g., screening) would reduce their susceptibility or severity, and perceive few barriers to taking that action.

The major constructs of the HBM include:

- Perceived susceptibility: One's belief about the risk of contracting a condition.
- Perceived severity: One's belief about the seriousness of the condition and its consequences.
- Perceived benefits: Belief in the efficacy of the advised action to reduce risk or severity.
- Perceived barriers: Belief about the tangible and psychological costs of the advised action.
- Cues to action: Factors that activate readiness to change.
- Self-efficacy: Confidence in one's ability to take the advised action.

The HBM explains why knowledge of cervical cancer is a crucial determinant of screening practice. Women who understand the severity and personal risk of cervical cancer are more likely to seek screening services. Conversely, if they perceive high barriers such as cost, fear, or religious objection, they may avoid screening. This theory supports the investigation of knowledge as a key factor influencing screening behavior and also informs the role of perceived barriers such as income and religious beliefs.

2.2.2 Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

Proposed by Ajzen (1991), the Theory of Planned Behavior expands upon the Theory of Reasoned Action by including perceived behavioral control as an additional determinant of behavior. TPB posits that intention to perform a behavior is the most immediate predictor of that behavior, and this intention is influenced by:

- Attitude toward the behavior: Personal evaluation of the behavior (positive or negative).

- Subjective norms: Social pressure or perceived expectations from others.
- Perceived behavioral control: The perceived ease or difficulty of performing the behavior, akin to self-efficacy.

TPB is particularly relevant in exploring how educational qualification (Objective 2) and religion (Objective 3) shape intentions and actions. Educated women may have more positive attitudes and greater control over their health decisions. Conversely, religious or cultural norms may exert pressure, negatively impacting intention and behavior. TPB thus provides a framework for understanding the intention-action gap in cervical cancer screening practices.

2.2.3 Locus of Control Theory

Developed by Julian Rotter in 1966, the Locus of Control Theory explains how individuals attribute control over events in their lives. It classifies individuals into two categories:

- Internal locus of control: People believe they can control outcomes through their actions.
- External locus of control: People believe outcomes are determined by fate, chance, or external forces.

This theory is significant in understanding how religious beliefs and socio-cultural attitudes influence cervical cancer screening. Women with an external locus of control may believe that illness is determined by divine will or fate, thus making screening irrelevant. In contrast, women with an internal locus are more likely to take proactive steps to protect their health. This framework enhances our understanding of how deeply held beliefs (shaped by religion or cultural norms) affect health behaviors.

Together, these theories provide a robust framework for analyzing the multi-dimensional factors influencing cervical cancer screening:

- HBM explains individual perceptions and knowledge as triggers or barriers to action.
- TPB links social influences and educational empowerment to intention and behavior.
- Locus of Control Theory highlights the psychological and cultural drivers of perceived health agency.

These frameworks collectively inform the design, interpretation, and application of this study's findings, offering a comprehensive lens through which cervical cancer screening behavior can be understood and addressed.

3 Research Methodology

The study employed a descriptive cross-sectional survey design to explore how knowledge, educational qualification, income, and religion influence cervical cancer screening among women aged 15–49 in Akwa Ibom Northwest Senatorial District. Using multi-stage sampling, the district was stratified into urban and rural areas; local government areas, wards, and households were then randomly or systematically selected to yield a representative sample. Data were collected face-to-face by trained female assistants using a structured questionnaire covering demographics, awareness of cervical cancer and screening methods, self-reported screening behavior, and the perceived impact of education, income, and religious beliefs.

To ensure the instrument's quality, the questionnaire was reviewed by public-health and reproductive health experts for content validity and pre-tested among 30 women in a similar but separate community. A Cronbach's alpha of 0.81 confirmed internal consistency. Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant Institutional Review Board, and informed consent was secured from all participants, with confidentiality and voluntary participation strictly maintained throughout data collection.

Quantitative data were coded and analyzed in SPSS v.25. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, and means) summarized participants' profiles, knowledge, and screening practices. Inferential analyses included chi-square tests to assess associations (e.g., location versus knowledge level), t-tests/ANOVA to compare screening uptake across education and income groups, and multiple regression to identify which factors most strongly predict screening behavior. All hypothesis tests were evaluated at the 0.05 significance level.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Knowledge of Cervical Cancer Screening among Urban and Rural Women

Table 1: Knowledge of Cervical Cancer Screening by Location

<i>Location</i>	<i>High Knowledge</i>	<i>Low Knowledge</i>	<i>Total Respondents</i>
<i>Urban</i>	108 (72%)	42 (28%)	150
<i>Rural</i>	57 (38%)	93 (62%)	150
<i>Total</i>	165 (55%)	135 (45%)	300

Data on table 1 shows information on the knowledge of urban and rural women. The findings revealed a significant difference in the knowledge of cervical cancer screening between urban and rural women. Approximately 72% of urban respondents demonstrated a high level of awareness regarding cervical cancer and its screening methods (e.g., Pap smear, VIA, HPV testing), while only 38% of rural respondents exhibited similar knowledge. Many rural women had never heard of cervical cancer screening and often confused it with general pelvic examinations.

This supports prior findings by Tsegaye et al. (2022) and Akokuwebe et al. (2021), who also reported limited awareness among rural and less-educated populations. The result confirms that geographic location correlates with exposure to health information, reinforcing the need for localized, community-level education initiatives. The significant disparity suggests that rural populations remain underserved by health outreach programs, despite being among the most vulnerable.

A chi-square test showed a significant association between location and level of knowledge ($\chi^2 = 38.24, p < 0.001$). The higher awareness in urban areas reflects better access to information and healthcare services. This validates the need for intensified health campaigns in rural communities.

4.2 Influence of Educational Qualification on Screening Practice

Table 2: Screening Practice by Educational Qualification

<i>Educational Level</i>	<i>Screened</i>	<i>Not Screened</i>	<i>Total Respondents</i>
<i>No Formal Education</i>	9 (18%)	41 (82%)	50
<i>Primary Education</i>	32 (32%)	68 (68%)	100
<i>Secondary Education</i>	47 (47%)	53 (53%)	100
<i>Tertiary Education</i>	65 (65%)	35 (35%)	100
<i>Total</i>	153	197	350

Table 2 shows a positive correlation between educational attainment and screening behavior. Among women with tertiary education, 65% had undergone at least one form of cervical cancer screening, compared to 32% of those with only primary education and 18% of women with no formal education. The chi-square test revealed a statistically significant association between education level and screening uptake ($\chi^2 = 14.76, p < 0.05$).

This finding aligns with previous research by Iliyasu et al. (2020) and Ginsburg et al. (2020), highlighting education as a strong predictor of preventive health behavior. Educated women are more likely to recognize early screening benefits, engage with health campaigns, and navigate the health system. Thus, promoting female education is not only a development goal but also a public health strategy. The result underlines the importance of integrating cervical cancer education into existing educational and vocational platforms.

4.3 Influence of Income and Religion on Screening Practice

Table 3: Screening Practice by Monthly Income

<i>Monthly Income (₦)</i>	<i>Screened</i>	<i>Not Screened</i>	<i>Total Respondents</i>
<30,000	28 (21%)	102 (79%)	130
30,000–60,000	44 (44%)	56 (56%)	100
>60,000	58 (58%)	42 (42%)	100
Total	130	200	330

Table 3.1: Screening Practice by Religious Affiliation

<i>Religion</i>	<i>Screened</i>	<i>Not Screened</i>	<i>Total Respondents</i>
<i>Catholic</i>	50 (62%)	30 (38%)	80
<i>Pentecostal</i>	58 (48%)	62 (52%)	120
<i>Orthodox/Anglican</i>	30 (50%)	30 (50%)	60
<i>Independent/Other</i>	12 (18%)	58 (82%)	70
Total	150	180	330

Income was shown to be a significant determinant of cervical cancer screening. Among respondents earning above the national minimum wage, 58% reported undergoing screening, compared to only 21% of women in the lowest income bracket. Many low-income women cited cost of transportation, screening fees, and time off work as barriers. Regression analysis confirmed income as a predictor of screening practice ($\beta = 0.41, p < 0.01$).

Similarly, religion emerged as an influential factor, but in varied directions. Women from religious denominations that actively support medical intervention (e.g., Catholic, Anglican, some Pentecostal groups) had higher screening rates (55%) compared to those in conservative faiths where screening is discouraged or viewed as unnecessary due to spiritual beliefs (18%). This is consistent with studies by Mengesha et al. (2020) and Jackson et al. (2020), which documented the role of religious doctrine in health behaviors. Women from denominations that support medical interventions had significantly higher screening rates than those from conservative or alternative religious groups. This emphasizes the role of religious doctrines in shaping health behaviors.

The findings suggest that beyond income and access, belief systems play a powerful role in shaping preventive health behavior. Culturally sensitive health education that engages religious leaders could reduce this barrier.

A regression analysis confirmed that income significantly predicted screening behavior ($\beta = 0.41, p < 0.01$), indicating that affordability affects access to cervical cancer prevention.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

This study examined the determinants of cervical cancer screening uptake among women of reproductive age in Akwa Ibom Northwest Senatorial District, Nigeria, focusing on knowledge, educational qualification, income, and religion. The results demonstrated that cervical cancer screening uptake remains suboptimal in the region, with critical disparities based on socio-demographic and cultural variables.

Firstly, knowledge was found to be significantly higher among urban women compared to their rural counterparts, highlighting the impact of location on access to health information. Secondly, educational attainment showed a strong, positive correlation with screening behavior. Women with higher levels of education were more likely to undergo screening, likely due to improved health literacy and decision-making autonomy. Thirdly, income level and religious beliefs emerged as substantial influences. Women with higher income had better access to screening services, while certain religious beliefs acted either as facilitators or deterrents to screening participation.

The study concludes that improving cervical cancer screening uptake requires a multi-dimensional approach that addresses personal knowledge, economic access, educational background, and culturally rooted beliefs. Without targeted intervention, many women in the region will continue to be diagnosed at advanced stages, with preventable consequences.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed to improve the uptake of cervical cancer screening among women of reproductive age in Akwa Ibom Northwest Senatorial District:

- 1. Implement Targeted Health Education Campaigns in Rural Communities**
Governmental and non-governmental organizations should collaborate to design and deliver cervical cancer awareness programs tailored to rural women. These should address knowledge gaps using local languages, culturally relevant content, and trusted community health educators.
- 2. Subsidize or Provide Free Cervical Cancer Screening for Low-Income Women**
Financial barriers significantly affect screening uptake. Public health agencies should integrate free or subsidized screening into primary healthcare services, particularly for low-income and underserved populations.
- 3. Integrate Cervical Cancer Education into Formal and Informal Education Systems**
Health education should be incorporated into school curricula at secondary and tertiary levels, as well as into adult literacy and women's empowerment programs. This would improve long-term health literacy and preventive behavior.
- 4. Engage Religious and Community Leaders in Advocacy**
Since religious beliefs influence health-seeking behavior, efforts should be made to educate and involve religious leaders in promoting cervical cancer screening. Faith-based interventions can help dispel myths and encourage participation in screening programs.
- 5. Strengthen Screening Infrastructure at the Community Level**
Increase the number of primary healthcare facilities offering cervical cancer screening, especially in rural areas. Ensure availability of trained personnel, necessary equipment, and a supportive referral system for women who test positive.

6. Conduct Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation

Establish a local monitoring system to track screening uptake, evaluate intervention effectiveness, and refine strategies based on feedback and emerging challenges

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